

TREATMENT OF SULPHATES-RICH SOLUTIONS THROUGH ETTRINGITE PRECIPITATION WITH INDUSTRIAL REAGENTS

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ABSTRACT. Mine wastewaters are often characterised with high concentrations of sulphates, heavy metals and increased electrical conductivity. It is mandatory for the industry to implement convenient treatment methods in order to reduce these parameters. The aluminium precipitation with the simultaneous formation of ettringite was chosen for laboratory testing as it is appropriate when the concentrations of sulphates have to be reduced – up to 300 mg/l according to the Bulgarian regulatory framework. In the present study synthetic waters were treated, as their composition was similar to that of typical mining effluents. Initially, the pH of the solutions was adjusted to 9.0 with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and thus the heavy metals precipitated in the form of hydroxides. Then, an aluminium source was added as Al-cement, industrial Na-aluminate or aluminium oxychloride. The best results in terms of sulphates and electrical conductivity decrease were obtained with Al-cement (69 – 100 % sulphates removal rate), but the quantities of the generated sludges were large, which raises the question of their proper disposal. With the industrial Na-aluminate the rate of removal of sulphates was very low and with AlOCl it was 96%. However, the use of both reagents showed an increase in the electrical conductivity of the treated solutions.

Keywords: ettringite, sulphates, removal

Introduction

At the mined sites with sulphide ores and during the processing of mining waste sulphide oxidation often occurs with the relevant negative impacts on water bodies - reduction in water quality (Bowell, 2004). Sulphates are produced from the exposition of pyritic rocks to air during mining activities (Liang et al., 2015). Thus, sulphate and acidity are formed (Equation 1).

Effluents from mining industry are often characterised by sulphates, heavy metals and electrical conductivity above the permissible levels. It is mandatory for the industry to implement convenient treatment methods for the decrease of these parameters.

The damage caused by sulphate emissions is not direct, since sulphates are a chemically inert, non-volatile, and non-toxic compound. However, high sulphate concentrations can unbalance the natural sulphur cycle. Sulphate is often the dominant contaminant of mine water and can form a wide range of salts and provoke salinity (Bowell, 2000). The accumulation of sulphate-rich sediments in lakes, rivers and sea may cause the release of toxic sulphides that can provoke damages to the environment. Together with bicarbonates and chlorides they form a major part of anions in natural waters (Benatti et al., 2009).

The existing mining water treatment technologies are generally poorly documented and not easily applicable. The processes of chemical treatment with mineral precipitation are usually the cheapest, but they produce the largest amount of sludge. Subsequent sludge reduction or recycling technologies have to be applied.

Chemical precipitation, combines different methods, as the classical approach is based on formation of precipitates using chemical reagents. A widely used method for sulphates removal from water is their precipitation as insoluble sulphate salts. The minimum achievable concentration of sulphates depends on the specific salt formed. Suitable compounds for removal of sulphates from water and sludge formation are Ca, Ba and Al.

The addition of calcium hydroxide or calcium carbonate to water for sulphate removal in the form of gypsum (Equations 2 and 3) is an attractive method in many aspects - low cost, easily operable, sludge removal.

The main process deficiencies are the high solubility of calcium sulphate and existence of interfering ions in the wastewaters. Gypsum is slightly soluble in water ($K_{\text{sp}} = 3.14 \times 10^{-5}$) and the sulphate concentration can be reduced only to about 1500 mg/l. This is a significantly higher concentration than the permissible values for surface waters. Considering the relatively high sulphate levels remaining in the treated water after reaction with lime or limestone, the process may be better suited as a pre-treatment step for acid mine waters.

Chemical treatment of mine waters using Ba salts has proved to be capable of removing sulphates to less than 250 mg/L (Špaldon et al., 2017) A separation can take place by a precipitation with barium (Ba) added as BaCl_2 , $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, BaCO_3 or BaS (Bosman et al., 1990).

Barite (BaSO_4) is highly insoluble making it an excellent candidate as a sulphate removal phase for sulphate treatment.

However, the Ba application is rather rare due to its limitations such as the high cost of the reagents, toxicity of barium salts and, in case of BaCl_2 , the free Cl-ion concentration after the formation of BaSO_4 .

If the concentration of sulphates has to be brought to lower level, aluminium precipitation with the simultaneous formation of ettringite is recommended. This results in low concentration of 50-100 mg/l sulphate as the ettringite is less soluble in water and can be used for removal (Pehlivanoglu et al., 1998). Ettringite is much more insoluble in water ($K_{\text{sp}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-45}$) compared to gypsum and removal of sulphate by precipitating ettringite could consistently reduce the sulphate concentration (Liang et al., 2015; Bowell, 2004).

Kiessig and Kunze (1996) proposed simplified chemical equations of the formation of ettringite during the sulphate removal. The overall process is presented in Equations 4 – 6.

The ettringite precipitation requires more complex chemical conditions to form sludges. Thus, this technology is more complex to operate. The operating parameters such as molar rates of calcium to sulphate and aluminium to sulphate along with pH have a crucial effect on the sulphate removal efficiency (Aygun et al., 2018).

The ettringite formation and precipitation requires blending of the aluminium source and the pre-treated mine water at an appropriate mass ratio of Ca:Al:SO₄²⁻ for 30 to 300 minutes as a reaction time. In practice, an excess (20%) of aluminium in terms of the stoichiometric requirements is dosed to enhance kinetics to achieve low residual sulphate concentration. Lime addition is also required to maintain the process at the optimum pH. A saturated limewater is fed at a controlled rate to maintain a reactor target pH above 11,5. The optimum pH for ettringite precipitation has been found to be around 12,0 (Kabdaşlı et al., 2015). After the precipitation reaction is complete, the ettringite solids are separated from the feed water, filtered and thickened.

Due to the high sulphate removal efficiencies of 85-90 % (Tolonen et al., 2016) and of over 95-98 % (Fang et al., 2018) the ettringite precipitation is a recognised method, appropriate to be implemented in industrial water treatment facilities. Worldwide, two commercial processes with ettringite precipitation for mine waters with sulphate concentrations over 2000 mg/l are often used - the SAVMIN Process and the CESR Process - Cost Effective Sulphur Removal Process (Walhalla Process). They both include heavy metals precipitation and gypsum formation as preliminary treatment step.

In the present study three different industrial sources of aluminium were tested, added to artificial waters with composition similar to typical mining effluents in order to reduce sulphate concentration, electrical conductivity and heavy metals contents in the treated waters.

Materials and methods

For the present investigation laboratory tests were carried out in a periodic regime by lime (as a preliminary step) and ettringite precipitation in order to optimise the chemical processes.

In previous analyses of real waters from a copper mining site in the Srednogorie region, low pH values were detected (in the range of 3,5 - 5,0), which is a deviation from the regulatory requirements according to Ordinance H-4/2012. Increased values of other indicators - electrical conductivity, sulphates, iron, copper, arsenic and zinc were also found. It was decided for the synthetic solution used in this experiment to have a similar composition - Table 1.

Each of the experiments was performed with 200 ml of synthetic solution with an initial concentration of sulphate 2,0 g/l.

The preliminary treatment of the tested solutions was performed by addition of 2% lime solution until the pH was raised to 9,00.

Table 1. Basic physical-chemical and chemical parameters of the synthetic solution

Parameter	Value
pH	3,80
EC, mg/l	1780
Eh, mV	315
SO ₄ ²⁻ , mg/l	2000,00
Water hardness, meq/l	785,00
Fe total, mg/l	5,50
As, mg/l	0,02
Cu, mg/l	2,75
Mn, mg/l	1,75
Zn, mg/l	4,00

A different source of aluminium is added to the separate variants. Ettringite precipitation was achieved at molar ratios of Ca/S = 3,20 and Al/S = 1,25 stated for being optimal in the literature (Dou et al., 2017; Tian et al., 2019), as the final pH was adjusted to 11,6 ± 0,1 using Ca(OH)₂ solution (2%). Three different sources of Al – aluminium cement, industrial Na-aluminate and AlOCl were used. The treatment with industrial reagents involved stirring for 30 min and 30 min of precipitation. The mixing of samples was performed by magnetic stirrers at 700 rpm.

After each phase pH, EC and sulphate concentrations were measured.

The additional study was performed with use of different concentrations of aluminium cement (5, 10 and 15 g/l). The time for reaction was divided by two, as the first phase includes stirring for 30 min and 30 min of precipitation, and the second one - additional 30 min of stirring and 30 min of precipitation.

In this experiment, a third phase was included - recarbonisation using carbon dioxide and adjusting the pH to 6,5.

The concentration of sulphate in waters was determined using a spectrophotometric approach (with BaCl₂ as a reagent) at a 420 nm wavelength. Samples of effluents were measured for pH, electrical conductivity (EC) and redox potential. The concentrations of Fe, As, Cu Mn, Zn, Al and Ca in liquid samples were determined through ICP-spectroscopy.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM-EDS) was performed in order to study the chemical composition of the sludges.

The volume of the precipitates was measured with conical flasks.

Results and discussions

Preliminary treatment

The treatment of water with lime is mainly aimed at the precipitation of heavy metals as hydroxides and part of the sulphate as gypsum. Due to the high solubility of gypsum, a reduction of EC to the necessary extent and sulphates could not be achieved (Table 2).

Data for the volume and weight of the formed sludge is presented in Table 3. The consumption of Ca(OH)₂ for neutralisation of the tested waters is estimated at 0,033 kg/m³ up to pH 9. The weight of the dewatered sludge is 0,13 kg at the lime treatment of 1 m³ of solution.

The chemical composition of the precipitates was obtained after they were examined with a scanning electron microscope equipped with a probe. The results are presented in Figure 1, as the elemental composition is presented in %. The sludge contains the heavy metals iron, copper, zinc, aluminium and manganese. From the data it can be concluded that the sludge is a mixture of different minerals, and iron is in the highest concentration among the heavy metals – 39,31%. Much of the sulphur is precipitated in the form of gypsum.

Ettringite precipitation

Ettringite precipitation was performed after removal of the sludge, produced from lime treatment. Additionally the pH was adjusted to $11,6 \pm 0,1$ using Ca(OH)_2 solution (2%). The quantity added from each of the Al-sources provides the optimal ratios Ca/S of 3,20 and Al/S of 1,25. The results obtained from the performed laboratory experiments with industrial reagents are presented in Table 4 and in Figure 2.

Table 2. Chemical preliminary treatment for heavy metals precipitation

Parameter	Initial value	Addition of 2% Ca(OH)_2
pH	3,80	9,00
EC, mg/l	1780	1717
SO_4^{2-} , g/l	2,00	1,997
Ca, mg/l	187,9	$797,9 \pm 1,0$
Fe total, mg/l	5,50	$0,104 \pm 0,001$
As	0,02	<0,010
Cu	2,75	<0,010
Mn	1,75	<0,010
Zn	4,00	<0,010

Table 3. Parameters of the precipitates from 1l of treated solution with 2 % Ca(OH)_2 up to pH 9

Sludge volume, 30 min, cm^3	3,5 – 4,0
Sludge volume, 60 min, cm^3	5,5 – 6,0
Weight of the dried sludge, g/l	$0,13 \pm 0,05$
Consumption of 2% Ca(OH)_2 , ml/l	$1,65 \pm 0,02$

Fig 1. Chemical composition in % of the precipitates after the preliminary treatment

Table 4 shows that when using Al-cement 64 % for sulphate removal was achieved, as the concentration of sulphate ions remained still slightly high. A decrease in the electrical conductivity of the solution was also observed.

Table 4. Sulphate removal with industrial reagents through ettringite precipitation (30 min stirring/30 min settling)

Reagent per 1 l of treated solution	SO ₄ ²⁻ , g/l	Sulphate removal, %
Al-cement, 4 g/l	0,72	64
Na-aluminate, 2 ml/l	1,34	33
AlOCl, 3,4 ml/l	0,087	95,65

Industrial Na-aluminate (liquid product) is also strongly alkaline and raised the pH to 12,6, which leads to the need for pH adjustment. The sulphate removal was very low - only 33%.

When using AlOCl (aluminium oxychloride) a high rate of removal of sulphates was achieved - 95,65%, but the reagent use resulted in a decrease of pH values to 3,9. The correction of the pH to the optimal values of over 11,5 for ettringite precipitation requires significant amounts of lime solution. It was found that industrial sodium aluminate and AlOCl, due to the characteristics of the reagents, lead to a significant increase in EC of the treated solutions (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Data on the change in the electrical conductivity of a synthetic solution at ettringite precipitation with the studied three types of industrial reagents

Due to the encouraging results for reducing the concentration of sulphates and electrical conductivity with Al-cement, it was decided to conduct more in-depth studies on the ettringite precipitation with different concentrations of the reagent. The results of the two-phase treatment (after the preliminary one) are given in Table 5.

These experiments also confirm the previous conclusions. The use of aluminium cement leads to effective sulphate removal and reduction of electrical conductivity, but significant amounts of sludge were formed (Table 6).

Table 5. Sulphate removal with industrial reagent Al-cement through ettringite precipitation

Al-cement, g/l	Initial EC, mg/l	First cycle (60 min)				Second cycle (90 min)			
		pH	EC, mg/l	SO ₄ , g/l	Sulphate removal, %	pH	EC, mg/l	SO ₄ , g/l	Sulphate removal, %
5	1706	11,55	1378	0,620	69,0	11,68	1306	0,030	98,5
10	1712	11,12	1349	0,445	77,2	11,63	1285	0	100
15	1695	10,90	1389	0	100	11,57	1279	0	100

Table 6. Parameters of the precipitates from 1l of the treated solution at ettringite precipitation with Al-cement

5 g/l Al-cement	
Sludge volume, 30 min, cm ³	100-110
Sludge volume, 60 min, cm ³	250-260
Weight of the dried sludge, g/l	10,385
10 g/l Al-cement	
Sludge volume, 30 min, cm ³	220-230
Sludge volume, 60 min, cm ³	300-310
Weight of the dried sludge, g/l	16,435
15 g/l Al-cement	
Sludge volume, 30 min, cm ³	440-450
Sludge volume, 60 min, cm ³	340-350
Weight of the dried sludge, g/l	21,52

Table 7 shows that for copper, iron, zinc and arsenic completely satisfactory levels were achieved, but the waters were still characterised by high concentrations of aluminium. It should be borne in mind that the solubility of aluminium hydroxide is strongly dependent on pH and when the pH dropped to 6,5, the concentration of aluminium in the treated water decreases significantly.

Table 7. Parameters of water after ettringite precipitation (second cycle) and recarbonisation

Parameter	After ettringite precipitation with 5 g/l Al-cement	After recarbonisation
pH	11,5±0,05	6,5±0,1
EC, mg/l	1362±5	1302±17
SO ₄ ²⁻ , g/l	0,03±0,008	0,046±0,010
Ca, mg/l	316,1±1,0	62,9±1,0
Fe total, mg/l	0,063 ±0,0006	0,104±0,001
As	<0,010	<0,010
Cu	<0,010	<0,010
Mn	<0,010	<0,010
Zn	<0,010	<0,010
Al	6,6±1,2	0,012±0,007

The composition of the precipitates includes Ca (35,99%), S (8,65%), Al (8,45%) and heavy metals – Fe (4,92%) and Cu (4,91%) (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Chemical composition in % of the precipitates after ettringite precipitation

Conclusions

The first step in the treatment of mining effluents rich in sulphate and heavy metals is liming. Thus, heavy metals and arsenic are effectively removed. The sludge formed contains gypsum and hydroxides of heavy metals. Due to the high solubility of gypsum, however, electrical conductivity and sulphates cannot be sufficiently reduced.

During the tested method of ettringite precipitation with industrial reagents, sodium aluminate and aluminium oxychloride cannot be used as the aluminium source. The best results in terms of sulphates and electrical conductivity were obtained in experiments with aluminium cement. In practice this is performed at the CESR process where a patented Al-containing product derived from cement production is used. However, the quantities of sludge generated are larger, which raises the question of their proper disposal.

References

- Aygun, A., Dogan, S., Argun, M.E., 2018. Statistical optimisation of ettringite precipitation in landfill leachate. *Brazilian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 35(3), 969–976. doi:10.1590/0104-6632.20180353s20170528
- Benatti, C.T., Tavares, C.R.G., Lenzi, E., 2009. Sulphate removal from waste chemicals by precipitation. *Journal of Environmental Management* 90, 504–511.
- Bologo, V., Maree, J.P., Carlsson, F., 2012. Application of magnesium hydroxide and barium hydroxide for the removal of metals and sulphate from mine water. *Water SA* 38(1), 23–28.
- Bowell, R.J., 2000. Sulphate and salt minerals: The problem of treating mine waste. *Min. Environ. Mgmt*, 11–14.
- Bowell, R.J., 2004. A review of sulphate removal options for mine waters: mine water 2004 – Proceedings Inter-national Mine Water Association Symposium 2, 75–91. Newcastle upon Tyne (University of Newcastle).
- Dou, W., Zhou, Z., Jiang, L.-M., Jiang, A., Huang, R., Tian, X., Chen, D., 2017. Sulphate removal from wastewater using ettringite precipitation: Magnesium ion inhibition and process optimisation. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 196, 518–526. doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.03.054
- Fang, P., Tang, Z., Chen, X., Huang, J., Tang, Z., Cen, C., 2018. Removal of High-Concentration Sulphate Ions from the Sodium Alkali FGD Wastewater Using Ettringite Precipitation Method: Factor Assessment, Feasibility, and Prospect. *Journal of Chemistry*, 2018, 1–8. doi:10.1155/2018/1265168
- Kabdaşlı, I., Bilgin, A., Tünay, O., 2015. Sulphate control by ettringite precipitation in textile industry wastewaters. *Environmental Technology*, 37(4), 446–451. doi:10.1080/09593330.2015.1026245
- Kießig, G., and Kunze, C., 1996. *Wasserbehandlung und Rückstandsentsorgung (Water Treatment and Waste Disposal, in German)*, *Geowissenschaften*, 14(11), November 1996, 481 p.
- Liang, H.C., Tamburini, J., Johns, F., 2015. Designing a Mine Water Treatment Facility to Remove Sulphate. 10th ICARD IMRA 2015.
- Pehlivanoglu, E & Kabdaşlı, Nuray & Tunay, Olcay. (1998). Sulphate removal by ettringite precipitation. *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin*, 7, 826–832.
- Špaldon, T., Hančufák, J., Sestínová, O., Findoráková, L., Fedorová, E., 2017. Barium Use for Sulphates Removal at Various pH Values. In *Thynieria Mineralna - STYCZEFfi - CZERWIEC <2017> JANUARY - JUNE - Journal of the Polish Mineral Engineering Society*. DOI: 10.29227/IM-2017-01-12.
- Tian, X., Zhou, Z., Xin, Y., Jiang, L.-M., Zhao, X., An, Y., 2019. A novel sulphate removal process by ettringite precipitation with aluminium recovery: Kinetics and a pilot-scale study. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 365, 572–580. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.11.032.